

Final Report for Master Module: High Temperature Electronics - Design and Manufacturing

Diode Lasers

Contact Materials and Joining Technologies for High Temperature Operation

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1. Analyses of the Problem

After the discovery of laser technology in in 1960s by Theodore H. Maiman at Hughes Research Laboratories [1], high power laser diode systems became popular in material processing, medical applications, and the pumping of solid-state lasers in recent years [2]. High power laser diode systems are typically made of an array of diode laser units a.k.a. laser bars, whose beams are coupled in order to achieve high output power [3].

However when laser diodes are operated at higher temperature, the performance and reliability deteriorates. This is due to strong dependence of the laser properties on the joining technology and contact materials. For instance, GaAs laser bar ($6.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) with indium solder material on copper ($16.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) heat sink material faces a serious thermo-mechanical stress, at high temperature, due to the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) mismatch (between GaAs and Copper) during the cooling process. A ductile solder material, like indium, can be chosen to compensate for the stress but indium itself is chemically unstable, undergoes oxidation and the ultimate fate is cracking due to creeping and as a result, short operation lifetime [4] or catastrophic failure [8].

Higher CTE miss-match relates directly with the higher operation temperature of the laser. High operation temperature must be possible for higher output power of the laser and therefore how high the output power of the laser will be determined by the operability of the laser diode at high temperature. This implies that overall performance of the laser diode at high temperature is determined by the inherent property of materials and technologies used for joining. This relation is portrayed on the picture below.

Figure 1: Relation between CTE, materials and performance

Therefore, the core task is to find out a good combination of a joining technology and contact materials that offer mechanical stability, high thermal conductivity and high electrical conductivity to make sure better reliability and performance of laser diodes at high temperature.

2. Subdivision of problems

2.1 Solder material and Bonding problem

A demand for higher efficiency solder material or technology is increased due to miniaturization [8] of semiconductor materials which in turn increased the need to handle high thermal density and current. Moreover due to the global restriction imposed on lead containing solder materials, to avoid environmental pollution, lead free solder materials are in demand[18][19]. Further, there is a constraint for operating temperature of solder materials. Solder materials can only be used reliably up to homologue temperature (T_h) 80% of their melting temperature (T_m) and operating temperatures must not exceed the homologue temperature limit. Strength of the solder will plummet drastically if the operation temperature exceeds this limit as shown on the figure below.

$$T_h = \frac{T_{opr.}}{T_m}$$

Where:

T_h = homologue temperature

$T_{opr.}$ = operational temperature

T_m = melting temperature

Figure 2: Homologue temperature [20]

Common lead free candidates for solder materials are categorized as, Tin (Sn)-based, Zinc (Zn)-based, Bismuth (Bi)-based and noble metal based (Ag, Au).

Drawbacks of these families of materials are listed on the following table:

Table 1: Disadvantages of common solder materials [18] [21]

Solder material family	Disadvantage
Zinc-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none">☞ High bonding temperature (420° C)☞ Poor ductility☞ Accelerated aging
Tin-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none">☞ Not reliable for > 200° C [24]
Bismuth-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none">☞ Low thermal conductivity☞ Low electrical conductivity☞ Brittle
Noble metal based	<ul style="list-style-type: none">☞ Expensive☞ Not the best thermal conductors for their price

Therefore a joining technology other than traditional soldering is required [19] and it is discussed on the solution section.

2.2 Heat sink material problem

The development of heat sink, a.k.a heat spreader, and thermal management system traces back to the need to improve a reliability in microelectronic components. This is because failing to effectively remove the heat will cause a sharp temperature rise which in turn will cause momentous degradation of operation and performance. In the worst case this sharp rise in a temperature can result in catastrophic failure [8] which is a total damage and failure of the electronic package.

The big challenge for heat sink is the odd behavior of materials with respect to thermal and electrical conductivity. Materials with highest thermal conductivity like carbon have poor electrical conductivity. On the other hand materials with high electrical and thermal conductivity, like Copper, cause severe mechanical stress problem due to their high CTE profile [9].

Therefore, the challenge is finding a material which can offer a good compromise for electrical and thermal conductivity while keeping mechanical stability.

2.3 Cooling system problem

The performance and reliability of the laser diodes strongly depends on the efficiency and the reliability of the cooling system as well. High operating temperatures can risk the life time of the laser diode [9] [11], for this reason it is important to have effective cooling system. However, cooling system will increase package volume, complexity, cost and chance of failure. For this reason it is even more desirable, if it is possible to do so, to build a laser system without cooling system [15].

2.4 Mechanical stability problem

Mechanical stability problem can be posed by built-in stress from the epitaxial layers, coatings, soldering process, and coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch (CTE) problem [14]. The joining technique also known as die [13] attach process causes mechanical stress during the cooling cycle if there is CTE mismatch between components. Once the laser diode is being in operation, mechanical stress will keep haunting the stability of the system as the laser goes through cycles of heating and cooling and the effect is severe for high variation on the temperature range.

3. State of the Art

A myriad number of works have been done for high temperature, performance and reliability of diode lasers. Various technologies for bonding are also available as soldering, sintering, brazing, NanoFoil®, PFDS400 ® [18] [25].

Various heat sink and cooling system have been developed so far [2] [3] [4]. State of the art high power laser diode technology employs micro-channel heat sink which has fine grids of channels for efficient cooling and for lower output power (< 50 W) conductive cooling is being employed [3].

There is no complete solution in a single work, but an improvement on a specific part of the laser diode technology as such the soldering (bonding) technique, heat sink technologies, beam quality, etc.

4. Available Solution

4.1 Bonding solution

Alternative bonding technologies to traditional solder materials which can offer better performance and reliability. These bonding technologies are silver sintering, reactive bonding (trade mark NanoFoil®), TLP- bonding and diffusion soldering process (trade mark PFDS400® PreForm based Diffusion Soldering technology for applications above 400° C) [18].

Comparison of these bonding technologies is presented on the table below:

Table 2: Comparison of bonding technologies [18][21]

Technology	Advantages(+) and Disadvantages (-)
Silver(Ag) Sintering	+Reliable + very high junction temperature + high thermal conductivity - requires high pressure (40Mpa), can damage the chip - if processed without pressure (or insufficient pressure) will form large number of voids - high cost - high electro migration
NanoFoil®	+ Reliable +very high re-melting points (enables formation of inter-metallic phases) - expensive process
TLP- bonding	+ inexpensive + low processing temperature + high re-melting temperature - time consuming slow process (commonly 60 min)
Ultrasonic assisted TLP-bonding [21]	+ short time(fast process) + very low processing temperature
Diffusion soldering process (PFDS400®)	+ Reliable + forms complete intermetallic phases(compounds) at the joint + soldering temperature below 250° C + process duration 5 minute

Parameter	Conventional soldering		Paste based diffusion soldering	Ag sintering	Reactive bonding (NanoFoil®)	PFDS400®
	Sn-solder	↑ Pb containing solder				
Process Temp.	< 250°C	< 360°C	< 300°C	< 300°C	> 1000°C	< 250°C
Process pressure	-	-	-	10 - 30 MPa	-	-
Process flux	fluxless / with	fluxless / with	with	with	-	fluxless
Process time	fast	moderate	moderate - long	moderate	very fast in s	fast
Max. operating Temp.	< 150°C	< 250°C	400°C - 800°C	961°C	> 900°C	400°C - 800°C
Thickness [μm]	10 - 500	10 - 500	10 - 100	desired thin, 10	nm scale	10 - 300
Voids	↓ voids	↓ voids	high	with pressure: low Pressure-less: high	-	↓ voids
Serial production	yes	yes	high	yes	x	yes
Process cost (production + bonding)	Low	moderate	moderate	very high	very high	Low
Material cost	moderate	low	low - moderate	very high	high	moderate

Figure 3: Comparison between soldering and other bonding techniques for high temperature applications [18]

4.1.1 Production process of PFDS400®

PFDS400® composite materials are produced by a process known as accumulative roll bonding (ARB), a.k.a. severe plastic deformation method [25].

Step-1: Rolling: Three layers of high melting point lead free metals, in our case Copper (Cu) and Tin (Sn), will be cold-roll bonded together to form composite material. Choice of thickness of initial layers is so that the final product will have full formation of inter metallic phases with the minimum possible minutes. Rolling process will continue with the product from the previous step until a desirable thickness is achieved.

Step-2: Soldering: Composite material will be placed between components to be joined, in our case, heat sink material and GaAs laser diode. Soldering process carried out in vacuum reflow furnace under reducing atmosphere of formic gas with max temperature 250° C. This process is portrayed on the figure below:

Figure 4: Production process of PFDS400 [18]

4.2 Heat sink solution

For a big breakthrough in a heat sink technology one must come up with a material that can exceed the thermal conductivity of Copper while keeping its high electrical conductivity. While there are some materials, like Vapor grown carbon fibers, with a thermal conductivity twice as much to that of copper but yet they are not desirable for their poor electrical behavior [9]. Copper does not fit well for a heat sink material, despite its good balance for thermal and electrical conductivity, simply because of its CTE profile does not match up with GaAs. Comparison of heat sink materials is shown on the table below:

Table 3: Heat sink materials comparison [5] [9]

Heatsink Materials Comparison		
Materials	Advantage	Disadvantage
Copper (Cu)	+ very good thermal conductivity (400 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) + very good electrical conductivity	- high CTE miss-match with GaAs (15.9 ppm/°C) [8] - high density - corrosion in water cooled systems [16]
Aluminium (Al)	+ thermal conductivity better than Cu-W (200 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	- high CTE miss-match
Copper-Tungsten (Cu-W)	+ low CTE miss-match (6.5)	- poor thermal conductivity (≈160 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) [9]
Copper-Molybdenum(Cu-Mo)[9]	+ low CTE miss-match	- poor thermal conductivity (≈180 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) [9]
Vapor grown carbon fibers (VGCF) *Carbon-composite material	+ Excellent thermal conductivity (800 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) i.e. 2 X more than Cu, 10X more than Cu-W + light weight (<2g/cm ³) + high *anisotropy [9]	- Poor electrical conductivity[11]
Diamond Aluminium Composites [9]	+high thermal conductivity (600 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	- Surface roughness problem - very expensive
CuSiC [8] * *MMC	+ good thermal conductivity (250 to 325 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) ++ adjustable CTE +light weight (3X lighter than Cu) + easy to process + better reliability (than copper)	- less thermal conductivity than Copper (almost half of Copper's)

***Anisotropy**: the property (heat in our case) of being directionally dependent, which implies different properties in different directions [10], i.e. different heat flow behavior in different directions.

This is advantageous because the mounting can be done in a way so that the heat will flow towards the direction of the heat sink and avoid unnecessary side way flow of heat. But yet it is disadvantageous as it cannot spread the heat i.e. should not be used as heat spreader.

The Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) process offers the best solution to produce heat sink materials because of its flexibility to adjust the CTE of the resulting material. This is because it is possible to adjust the CTE behavior of the resulting composite material by varying the composition and controlling the MMC process. The figure below depicts the CTE range for different materials and the MMC process respectively.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivity vs. CTE of selected thermally enhanced materials [8]

Figure 6: The (Metal Matrix Composite) MMC process [8]

4.3 Cooling system solution

Active (convection) cooling	Passive(conduction) cooling
Definition: heat transfer due to the bulk movement of molecules within fluids such as gases and liquids [6].	Definition: the transfer of heat internal energy by microscopic collisions of particles and movement of electrons [7].

<p><u>Advantages</u> + the most effective +suits for high temperature operation +suits for high output power (suitable for >60 watt/ laser unit) [16]</p>	<p><u>Advantages</u> + less complexity + less cost + more reliable due to less complexity +suits for high temperature with good thermal conducting heat sink + no coolant required + suitable for low power applications and less degradation rate($10^{-5}h^{-1}$) [17]</p>
<p><u>Disadvantages</u> - Bulky - complex - requires coolant - more expensive -corrosion[11] -not suitable for low power applications (complex and costly)</p>	<p><u>Disadvantages</u> - Less effective for high temperature - less effective for high power output (suitable for <60 watt/ laser unit) [16]</p>

5. Evaluation and Conclusion

For CTE matching and mechanical stability CuSiC metal matrix composite heat sink material can be used along with PFDS400® bonding technique. The solution can provide an operation temperature above 400°C as shown on figure 3 from [18] with a good mechanical stability profile. Active cooling system can be then mounted beneath the heat spreader (heat sink) for high power output lasers (>60 watt/ laser unit).

The demand for progressive miniaturization of technologies in laser diodes as well as microelectronics will keep increasing the challenge for thermal management, mechanical stability and reliability issues to be prevalent for a foreseeable feature. It was not possible to find the exact price for the suggested technologies.

Over all it is clear that a compromise on heat conductivity can be made where as CTE behavior is very strict constraint which must be met as long as reliability has to be ensured.

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